

**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SACHET
AND BOREHOLE WATER IN KATSINA METROPOLIS**

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**BEING A PROJECT RESEARCH SUBMITTED to the DEPARTMENT OF
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DEGREE (B.Sc.) IN BIOLOGY**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this research work titled (COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME SELECTED SACHET AND BOREHOLE WATER IN KATSINA METROPOLIS) is the product of my own effort.. it was conducted under the supervision of Mallam Abdullahi Shehu Ado and has not been presented and will not be presented elsewhere for the award of degree certificate, all sources of references section used in this work have duly acknowledged.

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Include registration no.

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project title (COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME SELECTED SACHET AND BOREHOLE WATER IN KATSINA METROPOLIS) was written by IBRAHIM FIRDAUSI HARUN with Registration Number NAS/BIO/18/2133 under the supervision of Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado

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APPROVAL PAGE

I IBRAHIM FIRDAUSI HARUN with the Registration Number NAS/BIO/18/2133 hereby certify that this research work titled (COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME SELECTED SACHET AND BOREHOLE WATER IN KATSINA METROPOLIS) has been prepared and submitted to the Department of Biology, Al-qalam University Katsina which has been examined and approved as part of the partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor Degree (B. Sc) Biology.

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DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to Almighty Allah the creator and controller of universe for his guidance and guardian towards a beautiful beginning and successful ending of my academy year.

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ABSTRACT

Physico-chemical analysis 3 of sachet and 1 borehole water within katsina metropolis was evaluated. The turbidity was determined using a turbidity meter. The pH, conductivity, DO(dissolve oxygen, BOD(biological oxygen demand) values were measured by the electrometric method. The total dissolved solids were determined by gravimeter. The titrimetric method was used to assess the alkalinity. The results of the pH(8.647±0.214), concentrations of the turbidity(8.733±0.2520), conductivity value(165.667±6.02), DO (8.733±0.252) and BOD (6.333±0.404) T/A(0.367±0.115), TDS(560.00±6.557), Tem⁰C (26.1) were below the WHO/SON permissible limits. However, some of the pH and Biological oxygen demand values were above the WHO/SON threshold limits. Compliance with drinking water quality standards based on national/international. This study deals with the isolation and identification of microorganisms from some selected sachet, well and borehole water produced at Katsina metropolis. The total coliform counts of bacteria in the different water samples are presented in figure 3. The total coliform counts were highest in Lamama and chake sachet water sample with a value of $8.0(1.0) \times 10^2$ cfu/ml and $6.0(1.0) \times 10^3$ cfu/ml while the least counts of $1.07(0.01) \times 10^3$ cfu/ml were recorded in Jadeed sachet water. All the values for total coliform counts were higher than the WHO standard of zero per 100ml except value from Jadeed sachet water which lower than the value of WHO standard. A total of four samples were collected and brought to the laboratory.

- **Keywords:** DO= Dissolved oxygen, BOD= Biological oxygen demand, T/A= Total alkalinity, TDS= Total dissolved solids

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Water is needed by all forms of life, man, animals and plants. It is present in almost all parts of the earth, about three quarter ($\frac{3}{4}$) of the entire earth's surface is made up of water and it exists in three states; vapour, liquid and solid (J.M Symons *et al.*, 1998). Water supplies are derived from springs, rivers, reservoirs, boreholes and natural lakes. The water passes through the ground and during which it dissolves some minerals in rocks, suspended particles, and pathogenic microorganisms from faecal matters. These and other factors make water unfit for drinking leading to the problem of scarcity or insufficient potable water (Raymond, 1992). Good quality water is odourless, colourless, tasteless and free from faecal pollution. A reliable supply of clean wholesome water is highly essential in a bid to promote healthy living among the inhabitants of a defined geographical region. Safe and potable water supplies in urban areas in Nigeria are still inadequate in spite of four decades of independence and several efforts from various governments. The standard industrialization world model for delivering safe drinking water and sanitation technology is, however, not affordable in most developing countries (Goel, 2006). It was reported that in Nigeria, about 80% of all diseases and over 30% of deaths are water-related (Dada *et al.*, 1997).

Water is an essential component of life on Earth, which contains minerals extremely important in human nutrition (Versari *et al.*, 2002). However, the dramatic increase in population resulted in an enormous consumption of the world's water reserves (Ho *et al.*, 2003). Natural

contamination of water resources mainly results from normal geological phenomena such as ore formation (Al Fraij *et al.*, 1999).

Water is an essential requirement of life for drinking, domestic, industrial and agricultural uses. Its quality and quantity which vary over space and time are important components in the integral development of any area. Any change in the natural quality of water may disturb the equilibrium system and it would become unfit for designated uses (Ato *et al.*, 2013).

(Ombaka *et al.*,2012) reported that the protoplasm of many living cells contain about 80 percent water and most of the biochemical reactions which occur in the metabolism and growth of living cells involve water medium, hence it is referred to as universal solvent. The world industrialized standard model for delivery of safe drinking water and sanitation technology is not affordable in much of the developing world (Gadgil *et al.*, 2003).

The safety of drinking water is a worldwide public health concern. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 1.1 billion of the world's population does not have access to safe water. In addition, 80 percent of diseases and one-third of deaths in developing countries are due to the consumption of contaminated water (WHO, 2011). In Nigeria, it is reported that the incidence of acute watery diarrhoea is approximately 4.9 episodes per year and there are approximately 200,000 diarrhoea related deaths of children aged below five years with an average of 300 deaths per day (United Nations, 2012).

Due to the scarcity of safe drinking water in Nigeria, communities obtain their potable water in form of sachet water, popularly referred to as „pure water“. It is the most common source of drinking water in Nigeria, given that it is relatively cheap, accessible and generally perceived to be of better quality (Stoler, 2012). Drinking water industries in Nigeria, mostly owned by private

institutions obtain water from surface or underground sources and since both types of water can become contaminated by biological and chemical pollutants originating from point and nonpoint sources, it is usually followed by various treatments processes (Stoler, 2012).

When water is tested for Faecal or Total Coliform, the results are usually given as the number of colony-forming units per 100 millilitres (CFU/100 ml) of water sampled. No sample should contain Faecal Coliform or *E. coli*, and ideally, there should be no Total Coliform (WSIS, 2007).

Coliform bacteria generally belong to four genera of the Enterobacteriaceae family, *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella*. *Escherichia coli* are the most well-known coliform (Feng *et al.*, 2002).

1.2 Aim and Objectives

This study was carried out to Compare the physicochemical parameters of some selected sachet and borehole water in Katsina Metropolis.

Objectives

1. To determine the physicochemical parameter of sachet and borehole water which of the sachet and borehole water? Include location also.
2. To investigate the chemical characteristics of drinking sachet, well and borehole water include site and location.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

Lifestyle and economic well being. This research is centered in investigating the physicochemical analysis and quality of a sachet and borehole water consumed on katsina metropolis.

1.4 Justification

To justify the claims made on the particular past researches on physicochemical analysis and bacteriological quality of sachet water. E.g consumption of bacteria in water cause an effect on human health.

1.5 Research hypothesis

1.5.1 Null hypothesis H_0

There is no significant variation in the physicochemical parameter of water samples of some selected sachet and borehole water

1.5.2 Alternate hypothesis H_a

There is significant variation in the physicochemical parameter of water samples of some selected sachet and borehole water.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Physicochemical Parameter

Looking at the importance of understanding physicochemical properties of water in a water body for supporting various biota, a study was planned to find out the physicochemical status of sachet water. The following parameters are considered:

2.1.1 Temperature

Temperature is a measure of the intensity (not the amount) of heat stored in a volume of water measured in calories and is the product of the weight of the substance (in gms), temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the specific heat ($\text{Cal g}^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$). In general atmospheric and water temperature depending on geographical location and meteorological conditions such as rainfall, humidity, cloud cover, wind velocity, *etc.* The atmospheric and water temperature go more or less hand in hand (WHO 1999).

Water temperature is of enormous significance as it regulates various abiotic characteristics and activities of an aquatic ecosystem (Sisman 2017; Surajit M. and Tapas. D., 2014; Stouthart *et al.*, 1996; Ramchandra and Solanki, 2007).

2.1.2 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) consist of the material left in a vessel after evaporation of filtered sample and include different kinds of nutrients and minerals which are considered as useful parameters in determining the productivity of the reservoir. Total solids is the term applied to the materials left in a vessel after evaporation of a water sample on its drying in the

oven at a defined temperature. While Total Suspended Solids (TSS) is the material left in a vessel after filtration of a water sample. Total suspended solids range in size from colloidal to coarse dispersions and range from pure organic substances to those that are high too those in nature (WHO, 1984).

2.1.3 pH (Potential Hydrogen)

Hydrogen ions (acidic), as well as hydroxyl ions (alkaline), are the result of the ionization of water. Any change in the concentration of any one of these ions brings about a change in the concentration of the other. Therefore, a single scale of numbers, called the pH scale (measured on a scale of 0-14) is used to measure the acidity or alkalinity of the water and the number expresses the concentration of hydrogen ions indirectly (Michael, 1984). The pH changes in water are governed by the amount of free CO₂, Carbonates and Bicarbonate. These changes are accompanied by changes in other physicochemical aspects that in turn influence the quality of water (Mahar, 2003).

2.1.4 Electric Conductivity

The conductivity of water allows measuring ionic constituents of all types of water including surface waters, process waters in water supply and treatment plants. Conductivity is the ability of a solution, a metal or gas - in brief, all materials - to pass an electric current. In solutions, the current is carried by cat-ions and an-ions whereas in metals it is carried by electrons. How well a solution conducts electricity depends on a number of factors:

- Concentration of ions
- Mobility of ions

- Valence of ions
- Temperature

The conductivity meter measures the conductance and displays the reading converted into conductivity (WHO, 1984).

2.1.5 Alkalinity

Alkalinity is a chemical measurement of water's ability to neutralize acids. Alkalinity is also a measure of water's buffering capacity or its ability to resist changes in pH upon the addition of acids or bases. The alkalinity of natural waters is due primarily to the presence of weak acid salts although strong bases may also contribute (i.e. OH^-) in extreme environments. Bicarbonates represent the major form of alkalinity in natural waters; its source being the partitioning of CO_2 from the atmosphere and the weathering of carbonate minerals in rocks and soil. Other salts of weak acids, such as borate, silicates, ammonia, phosphates, and organic bases from natural organic matter, may be present in small amounts. Alkalinity, by convention, is reported as mg/L CaCO_3 since most alkalinity is derived from the weathering of carbonate minerals (Unanam and Akpan, 2006).

2.1.6 Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Dissolved oxygen is essential to the respiratory metabolism of most aquatic organisms. The dynamics of oxygen distribution in inland waters are governed by a balance between inputs from the atmosphere and photosynthesis and losses from the chemical and biotic oxidations. DO is a very important parameter for the survival of fishes and other aquatic organisms. It is also needed for many chemical reactions that are important for Lake functioning (Oxidation of metals, decomposition of dead and decaying matter, *etc.*). (Ramchandra and Solanki, 2007).

2.1.7 Turbidity

Turbidity is the cloudiness or haziness of a fluid caused by large numbers of individual particles that are generally invisible to the naked eye, similar to smoke in the air. The measurement of turbidity is a key test of water quality. Fluids can contain suspended solid matter consisting of particles of many different sizes. While some suspended material will be large enough and heavy enough to settle rapidly to the bottom of the container if a liquid sample is left to stand (the settleable solids), very small particles will settle only very slowly or not at all if the sample is regularly agitated or the particles are colloidal. These small solid particles cause the liquid to appear turbid.

Turbidity is also applied to transparent solids such as glass or plastic. In plastic production, haze is defined as the percentage of light that is deflected more than 2.5 from the incoming light direction. (Haze technical definition, 2015)

2.1.8 Biological Oxygen Demand

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is the amount of dissolved oxygen (DO) needed (i.e. demanded) by aerobic biological organisms to break down organic material present in a given water sample at a certain temperature over a specific time period. The BOD value is most commonly expressed in milligrams of oxygen consumed per litre of the sample during 5 days of incubation at 20 °C and is often used as a surrogate of the degree of organic pollution of water.

(Clair N *et al.*, 2003)

2.2 Physicochemical Analysis

Is a method of investigating physicochemical systems that makes possible a determination of the nature of the interactions between the components of a system through a study of the relations between the system's physical properties and composition. The physicochemical analysis involves the measurement of various physical properties of the system, most often phase transition temperatures and other thermal properties (thermal conductivity, heat capacity, thermal expansion), electrical properties (conductivity, dielectric permittivity), and optical properties (refractive index, rotation of the plane of polarization of light). Also measured are the density, viscosity and hardness, as well as dependence of the rate of the transformations occurring analysis and techniques of microscopic metallography are extensively used in the physicochemical analysis. (Kurnakov *et al.*

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS

3.1.1 EQUIPMENT

1. pH meter
2. Test tubes
3. Conical flasks
4. TDS meter
5. Micropipette and tips
6. Sample bottles
7. Turbidity meter
8. Weighing balance
9. Spatula
10. Distilled water
11. Water samples
12. Cotton wool

3.1.2 GLASSWARES

1. Conical flask

2. Glass test tubes

3.1.3 REAGENT

1. Decolorizing agent

2. Hydrogen peroxide

3.1.4 MEDIA

1. Nutrient agar

3.2 METHODOLOGY

3.2.1 SAMPLE COLLECTION

Samples were carried out in different types of companies. 3 sachet water and borehole water within katsina metropolis. They are; Jadeed sachet water (JSW), Lamama (LSW), Chake sachet water (CSW) and Borehole water (BW).

3.2.2 PHYSIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

3.2.1.1 pH

The pH of each water sample collected was taken using a pH meter.

3.2.1.2 Turbidity

The turbidity of each water sample collected was taken using a turbidity meter.

3.2.1.3 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)/ Temperature/Electric Conductivity

The total dissolved solids, temperature and electric conductivity of each water sample collected were taken using a TDS meter.

3.2.1.4 Dissolved Oxygen and Biological Oxygen Demand

Dissolved oxygen and Biological Oxygen Demand was determined using a Hanna dissolved oxygen meter (HI 98186). For biological oxygen demand, sampled water was incubated for five days in the cupboard and Dissolved oxygen was also tested. The difference between the initial value of dissolved oxygen and the value after incubation gave the value of the biological oxygen demand in the water sample.

Where: DO_1 = Dissolved oxygen value at day one

DO_2 = Dissolved oxygen value at day five

3.2.1.5 TOTAL Alkalinity

One hundred (100)ml of water sample was transferred into a conical flask at 250ml capacity and three(3) drops of Bromo-cresol green-methyl red indicator were added respectively. The mixture was swirled and titrated against the solution of H_2SO_4 until colour changed.

Total alkalinity in $CaCO_3$ mg/l = titer value x 10

3.2.3 SERIAL DILUTION

Four test tubes were used for each water sample collected for the serial dilution. Distilled water was used as the solvent/medium for dilution. 9ml of distilled water was poured into each of the four test tubes for each water sample collected. 1ml of each water sample was added into four test tubes respectively. The test tubes were labelled as 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} respectively. 1ml was taken from the first test tube (10^{-1}) to the second test tube, 1ml was taken from the second (10^{-2}) to the third and another 1ml was taken from the third (10^{-3}) to the fourth (10^{-4}). Two Test tubes (10^{-2} and 10^{-3}) were used for culturing respectively. (Brown DF *et al.*, 2005).

3.2.4 MEDIA PREPARATION

Nutrient agar was used as the media for the analysis. The required dried media was measured in grams using a weighing balance and dissolved in water depending on the required ml of water in a conical flask. The conical flask was closed tightly using cotton wool and foil paper and it was then autoclaved at 121°C for 15mins. (Daniel, 2016).

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 RESULTS

TABLE 1.0: Mean and standard deviation of physicochemical parameters of sample from different sachet, well and borehole water in Katsina Metropolis.

SAMPLE	DO	ELEC.C	BOD	TEMP.	pH
JD	5.467±0.208 ^a	126.667±6.11 ^a	4.433±0.503 ^a	25.833±0.57 ^a	7.153±0.041 ^a
CH	8.733±0.252 ^b	145.333±6.42 ^b	5.133±0.206 ^a	24.833±1.58 ^b	7.407±0.075 ^a
LM	7.533±0.404	116.667±6.11	3.967±0.862	25.067±0.66	
BH	8.367±0.451	164.333±14.01	6.333±0.404	23.60±0.012	

KEY: DO= dissolved oxygen, ELEC.C= electric conductivity, BOD= biological oxygen demand, TEMP= temperature. JD= jade sachet water, CH= chake sachet water, LM= lamama sachet water, BH= borehole water.

Values are means o 3 triplicate determination ± S.D means with different superscripts along the same horizontal array differ significantly (P< 0.05).

TABLE 2.0: Mean and standard deviation of physic chemical parameters of sample from different sachet and borehole water in Katsina Metropolis.

SAMPLE	TB	TDS	T/A	ODOR	APPEARANCE
JD	5.20±0.17300 ^a	64.000±4.583 ^a	0.367±0.115 ^a	Odorless	Clear
CH	8.733±0.2520 ^b	66.000±3.606 ^a	0.300±0.436 ^a	Odorless	Clear
LM	110.0±8.0000 ^{bc}	59.333±4.041 ^d	0.300±0.011 ^a	Odorless	Clear
BH	149.00±3.606 ^{bd}	104.00±1.000 ^{bc}	0.267±0.115 ^c	Odorless	Clear

Include keys

4.2 DISCUSSION

The physicochemical parameters were examined in terms of physical content using the standards procedure of the American Public Health Association (APHA, 2005). There is a generally narrow range in pH values between the Ten samples of water types. In all the sachet, well and borehole water samples, pH values ranged between 7.0-8.65, with an average value of 8.647 ± 0.214 and 7.767 ± 0.283 in Borehole water respectively. These findings corroborate by the results of (Ruma, 2011), who reported the pH of the water samples ranging from 6.0-9.0 selected sachet water in Katsina metropolis.

The Turbidity of water sample range from 1.9-200. The highest turbidity value was observed in Chake sachet water (CSW) 8.733 ± 0.25

The dissolved oxygen of the water sample range from 5.00-9.00mg/L. The highest mean value of sample water is Chake sachet water (CSW).

The biological oxygen demand (BOD) range from 2.00-6.00mg/L. The highest mean value of the water sample is Borehole water (BW) 6.333 ± 0.404 All the values are above the maximum permissible limits set by WHO (2011).

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 discussion, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

It was evident from the study that sachet and borehole water sold in Katsina town at the time of the study met the recommended standards for physical and chemical qualities, but about 90% of the water brands were microbiologically unwholesome based on the WHO standard of bacterial limit. Since the microbiological quality of water is a hidden quality attribute that impacts seriously on public health, it is pertinent that the activities of regulatory agencies be intensified to ensure compliance with standards to avert public health hazards. Water is the essence of basic survival. Without it, life on Earth would cease to exist. When the quality of drinking water is good, human health is also good. The results obtained are supported with the conclusions that, the pH, EC, Turbidity, Alkalinity, BOD, DO, average values of the sachet water samples analysed within the acceptable limits set by WHO (2011) for safe drinking water. Microbiological assessment of drinking water quality should be done periodically with the regulatory body NAFDAC ensuring good quality assurance and maintenance of internationally defined drinking water standards. (Egwari LO, 2006).

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results obtained from this research, the microorganisms of the samples were stated and compared with the findings of other researchers. However, I wish to recommend on

1. Government should ensure that all the sachet water manufacturing companies should register with Government Agencies responsible for safe drinking water.
2. Further study on microorganisms causing waterborne illnesses.

4. There should be regular monitoring, inspection and sanctions by regulatory bodies to enforce existing water regulations.

5. Microbiological assessment of drinking water quality should be done periodically with the regulatory body NAFDAC ensuring good quality assurance and maintenance of internationally defined drinking water standards. (Egwari LO, 2006).

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APPENDICES

Plate 1.0: pH meter

Plate 2.0: Turbidity meter

Plate 3.0: Sample bottle

Plate 4.0: Dissolved oxygen meter